

Religious Abuse in Politics: Implications for Nigerian Democracy

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Abstract

The wave of religious intolerance has numerous adverse effects on Nigeria. Ironically, Islam and Christianity which are the dominant religions in Nigeria have a common cosmology. Both aspire towards achieving salvation by the gospel of love, peace and unity, and they project strict monotheism. But the opposite is the case. Very often, they are polarized and vehemently opposed to each other that sometimes the result is open confrontation. Most Nigerian politicians capitalized on this and use religion to achieve their selfish ends by aligning with any of the dominant religion to gain fame and power. This paper examines the wrong use of religion in politics and its implications for Nigerian democracy. The study employed qualitative research design in which data were sourced through books and journals. The work relies strictly on secondary sources of data collection and employed descriptive and analytical methods in unveiling the remote cause, consequences and remedy for sustainable democracy in Nigeria. The study found out that politicians are the cause of religious crises in Nigeria which led to hunger and establishment of IDP camps. The study recommends among others that leaders of these two dominant religions namely Christianity and Islam should discourage politicians from using religion in the negative way and encourage dialogue for peaceful and sustainable democracy in Nigeria

Keywords: Politics, sustainable democracy, religion

Introduction

Religion has always been manipulated for political ends particularly in Nigeria. The two major religions, Christianity and Islam dominate the political scene. However, the influence of religion on politics in Nigeria could be both positive and negative. In other words, as religion enhances national development, so also it could be counterproductive. According to Onaiyekan, in practicing politics in Nigeria, adherence to religious moral values and observance of Nigerian constitution, which makes provision for freedom of religion are necessary for achieving sustainable democracy in the county, it is often the belief of most discussants and theorists of Nigerian politics that Nigeria being a “secular state” ought not to have religious crises of the type that now characterizes the country.¹ The constitution of the country does not give preference to any of the two dominant religions: Christianity and Islam yet, the practices of successive governments give the impression of a country whose government has inclinations towards either of the two religions or both.

The religious inclination of successive Nigerian governments, particularly at the federal level of governance, continues to portray Nigeria as a religious state despite the secularity of its constitution. It is the involvement of politicians in religious matters that has been fueling or creating religious crises across the country, as each of the two major religions are visibly competing for political relevance. Religion, as volatile as it is, remains a veritable instrument for political manipulation in Nigeria. Politicians across the ethnic divide have

found religion more useful in mobilizing support for their candidacies or parties than ethnicity. There is a lot said today about separation of religion from politics. But this should not make us forget the fact that for most of human history, politics and religion have gone hand in hand.

In the great ancient civilization of the world, kingship and priesthood were very closely related. At times, it was not too clear whether we were dealing with a king with sacred powers, or a priest with political authority. The priest-king was a common phenomenon. Examples cut across all continents: the Egyptians in Africa, the Assyrians in the Middle East, the Greeks and Roman empires in Europe, and the Inkas in the Americas, to mention only a few.²

Similarly, in our African traditional societies, political life was shot through and through by religion. The rulers were agents of the gods of the land and custodians of the wishes of the ancestors. The people, on their part accepted the political arrangements governing their lives as religious obligations.³ The two religions which now jointly predominate in Nigeria are Islam and Christianity. Each has its own history of theocracy. Christianity, which started off as the religion of the slaves and powerless soon became a state religion in many places and remained so for a long time in some places even up till now. As for Islam, the phenomenon of the “Islamic state” has survived into modern times and is a subject of debate even in our land. The question of the relationship of religion and politics is therefore an inevitable and important one. The strident call for a separation of politics from religion often becomes a slogan used according to the convenience of the time. The reality is that both are tied together, by the very nature of things and this for at least two reasons. First, there is something inherently sacred about political power. History has shown that it can only be properly exercised when handled with sacred attention. In religious parlance, we say, “all powers belong to God.” Secondly, it is the same concrete human person who assumes both political and religious identity, and one necessarily affects the other.

This paper therefore aims at showing how politicians use religion in Nigerian politics and the implications for our democracy. In this attempt, religion is presented as two sides of a coin, with positive and negative implications. The paper has also made recommendations on how politicians can use religious values to improve the political life of Nigerian nation. To have a better understanding of the topic of this paper, some key words need to be clarified through their definitions. Hence, terms worthy of clarification are Religion, Politics and Democracy.

Politics

The original Greek roots of the word “politic” are *polis* “city” and *teche* “art, skill and, method⁴”. Etymologically, politics refers to the art of governing a city. It was believed that political life as an organized mode of living started in the city and spread to the neighbourhood. In this classical sense, politics is held to be the art of organizing men in a society to live and interact with one another for the realization of their social nature. In a wider sense, according to Omojuwa Ayodele Iyabo, politics refers to the processes by which people and groups acquire and exercise power.

It is commonly thought of politics as a feature of governments. But there is also politics in religious groups, educational groups, and scientific groups—in friendship groups and families. When power is organized and wielded through democratic, authoritarian, or totalitarian means, depending on how much participation states allow from citizens and how much control is exercised over the everyday lives of citizens.⁵ AkpenpuunDzurgba summed it up by defining politics as an activity. It is to him, a series of actions which is called a process. A political process is called a political system. A political system means a system of interactions. It is a platform for planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling and managing orderly interactions between individuals and social groups.⁶

Democracy

Democracy is a system which gives periodic opportunities for the masses to choose their leaders. Democracy is government of the people, by the people and for the people. Another definition of democracy is

that it is a system of government in which the will of the majority of qualified citizens prevails, democracy can also be defined as a majority government, or a government elected by the majority of the electorate (qualified adult citizens).⁷ There are two main types of democracy: Direct and indirect democracy. Direct democracy is where qualified adult citizens in a community, state or country participates in decision making directly without electing representatives. Indirect democracy is where the qualified adult citizens in a community, state or country elect members or representatives into the parliament who then take decisions on their behalf. This is the type of democracy practiced in this modern time. This type of democracy is sometimes referred to as “representative government.”⁸

Religious Issues during the Second Republic (1979 – 1983)

Although, one cannot ascertain whether or not religion played any noticeable role in determining the voting patterns of the Nigerian electorate during the 1979 elections, the influence of religion began to play out itself in the federal and state legislatures after the inauguration of the second republic. In some northern states where the ruling national party of Nigeria was in control of the legislature and the executive branch, policies were made to Islamise the governmental structures and even such policies were extended to areas of public life and public morality. The Sokoto state house of assembly for instance legislated against the sale of alcohol beverages in certain places in the state.⁹ This development spurred fundamentalist fervor in the state, as more groups began to champion the cause of promoting Islamic values at a broader national level beyond the limited confines of the state. The Sokoto phenomenon replicated itself in other northern states of the country.

Another very important development during the second republic was the outbreak of sectarian violence launched by a fundamentalist group known as the “Maitatsine.” In Dec. 1980, the Maitatsine group launched their violent “War against infidels,” which resulted in the death of not less than 4,177 persons and the destruction of properties worth millions of naira. It was after the intervention of the army and the Airforce that the eleven-day riots were quelled. About 1,000 members of the group were arrested and remanded in prison custody until October 1, 1982, when president Shagari granted them state pardon. Barely four weeks after their release on October 30, the fanatics again went on a rampage and struck at Bulunkutu on the outskirts of Maiduguri in Borno state. About 400 people including 16 policemen were killed in that riot. The question is how you can handle such a deadly group with kids gloves if not for political and religious manipulations.¹⁰

The recurrence of Maitatsine revolt following closely after the last one was worrisome. This was more so, because Nigeria does not have a Shiite Muslim population reputed for Islamic fundamentalism. But as it turned out, it seems the Maitatsine represents a subtle form of protest movement which utilizes Islamic symbol for effect and relevance. It was in an attempt to grapple with the challenges of these seemingly recurring religious crises fermented by a set of Islam, that President Shagari expressed his intention to establish a special advisory board on Islamic affairs under his office. The board was charged with the responsibility of advising the government on all matters affecting the welfare of Muslims in the country¹¹. It is on record that Christians and other non-Muslims in the country criticized the step taken by Shagari government as one meant to turn Nigeria into a Muslim state. As expected, Muslim groups and their leaders were derisive of the protest by Christians.

Consequently, as a way of stemming the raging controversies regarding the proposed establishment of an advisory board on Islamic affairs, president Shagari stalled the idea and instead appointed assistants for Islamic and Christian affairs. It is important to point out here that despite president Shagari’s posturing as an unbiased mediator in Christian Muslim conflicts, he also exploited the religious sentiments when in his 1983 re-election campaign speeches for the second term, which he gave in northern states where Muslims are in the majority he urged the people not to vote for infidels, apparently referring to the Christians presidential candidates¹². Thus, the landslide victories recorded by President Shagari in the northern states which partly earned his re-election was a function of his ability to whip up religious sentiments therefore, rather than reduce the salience of religious bigotry in Nigeria’s national politics, the Shagari administration entrenched it, by portraying it as a potent instrument for mass mobilization.¹³ Religions specialize in building one-faith exclusive brotherhood communities; religion, at

some point, is politics and is the most potent and long-lasting political association. Moreover, religious creeds excite and extract the deepest possible emotional and physical loyalties from their adherents when in political competition with people of other faith.¹⁴ Moshood Abiola, the newly crowned Baba Adini of Yorubaland, decided to open the Sharia debate in 1985. He did this when he began to campaign for the introduction of Sharia courts in the south.

It is not accidental that this coincided with his political misadventures and frustrations with the northern ruling class in the north whom he had sided with hoping that the religious cord would enhance his chances in the second republic. Abiola certainly saw a sense in seeking a greater hold among his Yoruba tribe through the religious cord. But the question was, did the south or better still, Yoruba land need Sharia courts or was chief Abiola seeking extra political mileage and preparing his political nest? Other Muslims saw through the political opportunism of chief Abiola. According to Junaidu Mohammed "Abiola's religious posturing have no religious motives; religion for him is one more political ammunition, one avenue for the centre of power. He considers religion like a plaything, a past time."¹⁵

In the same vein Arthur Nzeribe in his campaign in 1992 called on all Christians to unite and elect a Christian president.¹⁶ During the fourth republic, the Obasanjo/Atiku regime was Christian/Muslim; Yar'adua/Jonathan was Muslim/Christian; Jonathan/Sambo was Christian/Muslim; Buhari/Osinbajo is Muslim/Christian. In subsequent political dispensations, religion has been a sensitive factor in choosing principal officers at the two levels of national assembly these instances shows that political parties and administrations recognized religion as a factor in governance.¹⁷ It is an issue that voting and campaign, in some cases, are based on religious sentiment. In this case, religion could be used to either canvas support for a candidate or dissuade the electorate from voting for him or her. This is why some Christians will not support Muslim candidates and vice versa.

In 2003, Major General Muhammadu Buhari, of All Nigerian People's Party, was criticized for his stand on religious matters and this, no doubt, worked against his political fortune. As a perceived advocate of the Sharia law and fundamentalist, he was quoted to have said Muslims should not vote for Christian candidates. This could contribute to the reasons why he lost the 2011 presidential election in Nigeria. From the foregoing, it can be inferred that religion could be a dangerous factor in an electoral process.¹⁸

Implications of Religious Influences on Nigerian Politics for Sustainable Democracy

The influence of religion on Nigerian politics has both positive and negative implications. The implications can be considered as follows:

Positive influence

The positive influence of religion on politics is that it enhances sustainable democracy and national development. In this sense, one expects religious ethical values to manifest at every point of influence. This means that religious people have a duty to abide by the ethical teachings, inherent in their religions and such, will provide good leadership and obedient followership. Religion provides mankind with moral values by which to live. According to Nnadi, "...religion is often used to subvert political needs and aspirations of the ruling class. Religion if positively used to promote the political life of any society."¹⁹ Every religion, whether Christianity or Islam has moral values which regulates and harmonize human life.

No religion condones immorality, highlighting the function of religion as a provider of moral values, Mbiti opine that "it is religion which tells what is right, and what is wrong...religion enriches people's morale for the welfare of the individual and society at large."²⁰ Adherence to religious ethical values is imperative for all religious practitioners. As posited by Ikenna I. Umeanolue, there is a need to live a moral life because it is commanded by God. Failure to do this will be counterproductive in the matter of sustainable democracy and national development.²¹ On his part, C.O.T. Ugwu affirms that, one expects a credible electoral process in a religious community, like Nigeria if the rules are obeyed. Religion, being an agent of social control, helps to keep with the norm, of the society, which is the real basis of politics.²²

Religion breeds an ideal heart in man to be conscious of the need to have a clean heart. By this, he will grow to have a philanthropic or patriotic thought before venturing to lead or represent his people in government of the state in another words, religion will prepare the mind of man to be a good politician who will constantly fall back upon his religion to guide him. The teaching or threats of religion are expected to guide him to be able to rule his people aright as a politician with fear of God in him. He will never consider himself first; rather he knows that he is the servant of the electorate.²³ Without mincing words, a hitch free election will produce legitimate leaders who will govern with the fear of God, and obedient followers. Achieving this will solve problems, such as political instability, violence and insecurity, maladministration, retardation of growth and development, and international stigmatization and apathy politics, which apparently are by products of electoral malpractices. Johnstone opines that; what one believes, with respect to that which is good, true, and desirable as well as what God intends for people and society, could be expected to influence the choice one makes in the political arena. That is, religion should affect people's voting pattern.²⁴

Negative Influence

The negative influence of religion on politics has, over times threatened the corporate existence of Nigeria. For example, the issue of the Sharia Court of Appeal almost brought the constituent Assembly to an abrupt end in 1978, given the walkout that was staged by some Muslim members and the antagonism of non-Muslims. This wouldn't, have arisen if the secular/pluralistic nature of the country had been respected. Religious crises have further worsened inter-ethnic animosity. The Kaduna and Jos ethno-religious crises displaced many people who had settled in the Northern part of the country for many years as it became necessary for them to relocate. Also, the adoption of Sharia law by some state governors almost terminated the National Youths Service Corps scheme, which for many years has been a major intergrading and unifying factor. The reason was that many southerners did not want their children or relations to be posted where they would be forced to obey Islamic law. The tension was doused when the general public was assured of their safety. The killing of some corps member serving in the north is another way of understanding this issue.²⁵

No society can grow in the atmosphere of religious violence which, more often than not, has political undertone. It should be mentioned that the 2008 and 2010 Jos crises started as a political war and it later took ethno-religious dimension in which several lives were lost. All these have economic implications on individuals, states, and the country, as a whole. Many people in the south do not see reason why taxes collected on businesses, prohibited by the Sharia law, should be used to develop states that operate it.²⁶

Still, on the economy, one may not be wrong to conclude that public money expended on religious matters such as pilgrimage activities, places of worship in government houses, and other public places, could have helped the ailing economy. Both Christian and Muslim politicians have failed in Nigerian politics since they cannot blend politics with religious values. Unfortunately, religion is often used to cause confusion, or pacify the electorate in Nigerian politics. Olusegun Obasanjo also played religious politics when he was the civilian president to the detriment of the masses.

According to Ugwueye, during Obasanjo's democratic administration, the link between religion and politics was very glaring from the vast use made of the Christian religion by the ruled and the ruler alike. Unfortunately, it was done, for the most part, for selfish interest, not for real religion reasons.²⁷ True democracy is dependent upon free, fair and credible election, a situation where by the electorates are free to elect their leaders. The elected leaders will in turn sustain the rule of law, which is the benchmark of any true democracy in a civilized society. Many of them are simply after what they stand to gain. Moreover, where people vote on religious sentiment, mediocre leaders are most likely to emerge and, when this happens, growth and development will be retarded and our nascent democracy will be in danger of been taken over by the military. The negative impact of religion in Nigerian politics is increasingly manifested in the nation. Every political process in Nigeria has religious under tone. The civil service appointment to important positions in government and the entire body

politic of the nation are seriously influenced by religious prejudice. This ugly situation continues hindering our national development and putting our nascent democracy to danger.

Conclusion

This paper has established that there is religious influence on politics in Nigeria. These religious influences have both positive and negative implications for our nascent democracy in Nigeria. Our politicians are using religion more negatively to scheme things for their selfish benefits. This has caused a lot of tension and crisis in the country. One will notice or find IDP camps all over the country. These crises have religious undertone which is caused by our politicians. Government should handle religious issues with care and our politicians should be educated by these two major religions in the country to use religious values positively to sustain democracy in our country Nigeria.

Recommendations

Christians and Muslims leaders should endeavour to impress on their followers the teaching on the solidarity of humankind. Christians and Muslims leaders in Nigeria must continue to reach out and sustain the culture of dialogue and equally seek to educate its followers on the ills of violence in order to enhance peaceful and sustainable democracy in Nigeria. Both leaders and the led should adhere to religious moral values. Nigerian politicians should be discouraged by the electorates for using religion for their selfish ends by not voting base on religious sentiments but by credibility of the candidate. Religious issues should be handled with care by Nigerian Government. The culture of forgiveness must transcend words but be reflected in social relationship.

Endnotes

- ¹John Olushola Magbadelo, "The politics of Religion in Nigeria," in *The Journal of International Issues*, Volume 2 (2003), 64-88.
- ²John Olorunfemi Onaiyekan in *Religion Politics and Power in Northern Nigeria*, Matthew Hassan Kukah (Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited, 1993), vii.
- ³Matthew Hassan Kukah, *Religion Politics and Power in Northern Nigeria* (Ibadan: Spectrum books Limited, 1993), ix.
- ⁴Ota N. Ejitu, Chinyere S. Ecoma, Chiemela Godwin Wambu, "Creation of States in Nigeria, 1967-1996: Deconstructing The History And Politics". *American Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol 6, No. 1, (2020), 3.
- ⁵Omojuwa Ayodele Iyabo, "Christianity and Politics—Any Parallel Line? Christian Moral Point of View," *Intrenational Journal of Liberal Arts and Social Science*. Vol. 2, No. 7, September, (2014), 23.
- ⁶Akpenpuun Dzugba, *Nigerian Politics and Ethical Behaviour* (Ibadan: John Archers, 2008), 1.
- ⁷Dibie. C. Chris, *Essential Government for Senior Secondary Schools* (Ibafo: Tonad Publishers Limited 1999), 10.
- ⁸Ibid.
- ⁹Magbadelo, 64-88.
- ¹⁰Kukah, 6.
- ¹¹Ejitu and Ecoma, et al, 3.
- ¹²Familusi O. O, "Religious Politics and its Implications for Sustainable Development in the Post Independence Nigeria", *Journal of sustainable Development in Africa*, 210, 156-169.
- ¹³Falola T, "Violence in Nigeria: The Crisis of Religious Politics and Secular Ideologies" (Rochester: University Rochester press. 1998), 25.
- ¹⁴Obiefuna, B.A.C, "Religion and Human Relations in Contemporary Nigeria: The Wounds, the Healing", An inaugural lecture of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, 2018:
- ¹⁵Okafor V.E, "The Mutual Influence of Religion and Politics" In *Journal of Religion and Human Relations* (2007): 166-172.
- ¹⁶Matthew Kukah, *Religion Politics and Power...261*.
- ¹⁷Sodiq Y, "Can Muslims and Christians live Together Peacefully in Nigeria?" *The Muslim World*, 2009, 646-688.
- ¹⁸Onapajo H, "Politics for God: Religion, Politics and Conflict in Democratic Nigeria" In *The Journal of Pan African Studies*, (2012): 42-66.
- ¹⁹Nmah, P.E, "Religion and Politics in Africa: A Paradox" In *Journal of Religion and human Relations*, Maiden Edition (2007): 119-127.
- ²⁰Ikenna I. Umeanolue, "Religious Influences on Politics in Nigeria: Implications for National Development". [Http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/org.v15i1.9s](http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/org.v15i1.9s)

²¹Ibid.

²²C.O.T Ugwu, *Man and his Religion in a Contemporary Society* (Nsukka: Chuka Educational Publishers, 2002): 15.

²³Ikenna I. [Http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/org.v15i1.9s](http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/org.v15i1.9s)

²⁴R. L. Johnstone, *Religion in Society: A Sociology of Religion* (New Jersey: Prentice Hall. 2001): 10-13.

²⁵J. K. Ayantayo, *Religious Factors in the Nigerian Public Sphere: Burdens and Prospects*, *Africa Development*, (2009): 93-109.

²⁶J. O. Awolalu, "Religion and Society," in *Religion and State: The Nigeria experience*, A.S. Adewale ed. (Ibadan: Orita Publications 1988): 1-11.

²⁷I. E. Ugwueye, "Christian Faith and Politics during Obasanjo's Democratic Administration", in *The Humanities and Nigeria's Democratic experience*, A. B. Chiegboka, C. E. Nwadike and E. C. Umezina eds. (Nimo: Rex Charles and Patrick, 2009): 253-2590.